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FUNDAMENTAL STUDY ON FABRICATION OF C/C ROD
Tsuyoshi Ozaki, Mitsuhiro Okumura, Hiroyuki Teramoto,
and Kiyoshi Yoshizaki
Sagamihara Lab. c/o Mitsubishi Electric Corporation
Petroleum Energy Center
1-1-57, Miyashimo, Sagamihara 229, Japan

ABSURACT

Carbon/carbon (C/C) composites, composed of fibrous carbon substrates and pyrolytic carbon matrices, have received considerable interest for aerospace applications because of their superior properties at very high temperatures. Chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) is one of the suitable fabrication process in which fiber and matrix are less damaged. However, it takes much time to infiltrate into the woven carbon cloths or carbon felt directly, and it is difficult to infiltrate the porosity perfectly. So we try to fabricate C/C rods first, and composition of 2- or 3-dimensional C/C composites are followed by assembling and re-infiltrating them. In this paper, the basic CVI conditions of C/C rods such as infiltration temperature, gas pressure and proportion of gas mixture are examined. Pitch-based carbon yarns were resistively heated and methane and hydrogen were used as the carbon source and the carrier gas, respectively. The yarns were infiltrated successfully, and the texture and the microstructure of the pyrocarbon were observed by scanning electron and optical polarizing microscopy, respectively. The microstructures were mainly smooth laminar and isotropic materials were also obtained depending on the ratio of methane gas. The infiltration rate was found to depend strongly on the temperature of substrates and gas pressure, which suggests the possibility of fabrication of C/C rods in a short time by establishing the suitable conditions of CVI.

KEYWORDS: Carbon/Carbon; Unidirectional; Chemical vapor infiltration; Fabrication of Rods; Pyrolytic Carbon.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon-fiber-reinforced carbon (C/C) composites have outstanding properties such as strength retainment at high temperature and high heat resistance to abrasion, and are very hopeful materials for aerospace application. There are two principal methods for fabrication of C/C composites: (i) impregnations and carbonizations with a liquid organic resin or pitch, and (ii) chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) of pyrocarbon from a hydrocarbon gas (such as methane,

propane and benzene). C/C composites fabricated by the former method have been already applied as high temperature materials because of their good thermal shock resistance and relatively low fabrication costs. The strength and the toughness of them, however, have not been fully performed, because the weight loss and volume shrinkage of organic carbon matrix precursors during the pyrolysis result in porosity of composites and sometimes in damage of fibers and/or matrices. In the latter method, a hydrocarbon gas is diffused into a fibrous substrate and reaction of the gas into carbon occurs on the substrate at rather low temperature, and the damage of fiber and matrix is less than in the impregnation. Though the mechanical properties of C/C fabricated by CVI is better, it needs long fabrication time (generally 100 to 2000 hours depending on the type of substrate and the condition of CVI) due to the low deposition rate. In addition, because of the overcrusting of the outer surface by deposited carbon, interior of the large-sized substrates is not fully infiltrated. Several devices have been tried to improve these problems, and some of which including the temperature gradient process were reported to be effective for single-item composites (1,2). But it is difficult to fabricate larger and more complicated composites in a short time, and the fabrication cost remains high.

This study aims at establishing a new fabrication technique of C/C composites, in which unidirectional C/C rods by means of CVI are fabricated first, then 2- or 3-dimensional skeleton frames are assembled and C/C composites in final shape are obtained by impregnating and/or re-infiltrating them. In fabricating C/C rod, a bundle composed of 1000 to 6000 carbon fibers is introduced into the first reactance chamber and infiltrated at a certain CVI condition, then followed by more infiltration on the different conditions in the following chambers, and a C/C rod with very little porosity is fabricated in rather a short time. In establishing this fabrication system, it is important to obtain the favorable condition of CVI in each reaction step. This paper reports the fundamental conditions of CVI on C/C rod using a batch of carbon fibers and examining the influences of fundamental CVI conditions such as temperature of fibers, pressure of gas and proportion of gas mixture, and possibility of the efficient fabrication of a C/C rod is discussed.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Experimental Set-up of CVI Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of CVI system. A batch of carbon fibers cut from a roving is attached to the electrodes made of copper and resistively heated by the Joule effect. The interelectrode spacing is 0.05m and the maximum DC input power is 150W. The temperature of the substrate is measured by an optical pyrometer and kept constant during the infiltration time. The chamber is pumped by a rotary pump and the gas pressure is manually controlled by needle-valves from 1 to 20KPa. Methane and hydrogen are introduced into the reaction chamber, as a process gas and carrier gas, respectively. The flow rate of the gasses is controlled by flow meters from 0 to $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{m}^3 \text{min}^{-1}$, and the ratio of gas mixture is varied.

2.2 Substrates Substrates used here are pitch-based carbon yarns (Tonen FT-700) containing 3000 fibers which have an average diameter of approximately 10^{-5} m. The yarns are sized for fabrication of plastic matrix composites. The size, however, is not necessarily suitable for C/C composites, and some reports described that the strength of C/C composites increased by removing size. In this study, the yarns were submerged in hot water and size were washed off by an ultrasonic vibrator before infiltration. Scanning electric micrographs of the fiber are shown in Fig.2, and ESCA spectra of carbon fibers are shown in Fig.3. The ESCA spectrum obtained from the washed-off fibers is similar to Kojima's one obtained from PAN-based carbon fibers (3). From these results, the size of the substrates were found to be successfully washed off.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Thermal Distribution of Substrates Figure 4 shows electric power versus temperature of substrates. The temperature increases non-linearly, and more electric power (approximately 10% in case of 13.3KPa) is needed in the gas. Figure 5 shows the thermal graph measured with the thermal video system (Avionics, TVS-5000) when the deposition temperature was set at 1773K. Along the fiber, thermal gradient from under 373K up to deposition temperature is observed. This is because the electrodes are water-cooled and the thermal capacity of substrates is much smaller than that of electrodes. Similarly, thermal gradient across the yarn was observed. The range of temperature, however, is rather narrow (from 1473K to 1773K) because the yarn was cooled by the process gas alone.

3.2 Texture and Microstructure The texture of C/C rods is examined by scanning electron microscopy. Figure 6 shows the typical micrograph of the fracture surface (x2000). Pyrocarbon is well deposited among the fibers. Some pull-out of the fibers are also observed, which shows the weak bond strength at the interface between fiber and matrix. It has been shown that the microstructure of pyrolytic carbon matrices is varied by the deposition conditions such as the kind of hydrocarbon gas, the mixture ratio of hydrocarbon gas to carrier gas and the deposition temperature (4,5). Three types of microstructure (i.e.; smooth laminar, rough laminar and isotropic) are defined according to the optical anisotropy and texture roughness. Physical and mechanical properties of C/C composites depending on the microstructure of matrix carbon have been studied, and the smooth laminar has been reported to be advantageous to the elastic modulus and the bending stress (6). Figure 7 shows the result of optical polarizing microscopy obtained in this study. In case of temperature of 1773K and the ratio of methane of 50%, the smooth laminar structure was observed. On the other hand, the isotropic structure was deposited when the temperature was 1973K and the ratio was 5%. It agrees with the general tendency that low deposition temperature and high ratio of the hydrocarbon gas causes smooth laminar structure, and the isotropic structure is deposited on the opposite condition (1). In case methane is used as the carbon source, the range where isotropic structure is deposited is known to be rather small. In this examination, the ratio of methane was varied from 20% to 100% at the deposition temperature 1573K, 1773K and 1973K. Every microstructure of pyrolytic

carbon was smooth laminar, and the condition in Fig.7(b) was the only case for isotropic structure.

3.3 Influences of Infiltration Temperature Infiltration temperature examined here were 1373K, 1573K, 1773K and 1973K. Figure 8 shows the mass gain of carbon as a function of infiltration time when the total gas pressure was 4KPa and the ratio of methane was 50%. The mass gain increases as the infiltration time and is clearly affected by the infiltration temperature. At 1373K, the mass gain was very small at any time. On the other hand, obvious mass gain was observed all the time as well as a large amount of mass gain was obtained in a shorter infiltration time. The areas where pyrolytic carbon was infiltrated, however, were different depending the infiltration temperature. Figure 9 shows the scanning electron micrographies of the fracture surfaces of interior and near surface of the C/C rod after infiltrated 10 hours. At 1373K, deposition of carbon was very little near surface whereas a small amount of deposition was observed in interior. At 1573K, thickness of pyrolytic carbon near surface was almost the same as or a little larger than in interior. At higher temperatures, deposition occurred mainly near surface. Especially, at 1973K, no deposition was observed in interior while very thick pyrolytic carbon was deposited on the surface. These difference are also observed in the micrographies of cross sections of C/C rods (Fig.10). The mass gain at high temperatures is considered to be due to the deposition of carbon on the surface of the rod. At 1573K, the rod was well infiltrated both in interior and near surface, though the mass gain rate decreased as the time went by. In fabrication of C/C rods, it is found that the yarns should be infiltrated at 1573K or lower temperature first. After infiltrating interior, the rods can be deposited at higher temperature in order to reduce fabrication time.

3.4 Influences of Gas Pressure The mass gains when the total gas pressures were varied from 4KPa to 13.3KPa (ratio of methane was 50%) are compared in Fig.11. Though the amount of mass gain is not proportion to the total pressure, it is clearly increase as the pressure becomes high. The influences of the ratio of the gas mixture were also examined (Fig.12). The mass gain increases as the methane ratio increases, which should be the effect of partial pressure of methane, considering the microstructure of pyrolytic carbon is independent of the ratio in this range.

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, several fundamental conditions of CVI of C/C rods were examined and possibility of fabrication was confirmed. The results are summarized as follows:

- (1) Pyrolytic carbon was successfully deposited on the substrates, and the microstructure was mainly smooth laminar.
- (2) The deposition rate and the area where the pyrolytic carbon was infiltrated strongly depended on the infiltration temperature, which suggests the optimum conditions for each CVI step in case continuous C/C rods are fabricated by multi-stepped CVI process.

(3) Pressure of process gas also affected the deposition rate, and higher pressure was advantageous in the examined range (4.0 to 13.3 KPa).

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Fig.1 Schematic diagram of the experimental setup.

(a) As received

(b) After washed off

Fig.2 Scanning electric micrographs of the carbon fibers.

Fig.3 ESCA spectra of the carbon fibers.

Fig.4 Electric power versus temperature of the substrates.

Fig.5 Thermal distribution of the substrates.

Fig.6 Scanning electric micrographs of the fracture surface of the C/C rod after infiltrated 30 hours(1573K,4KPa).

(a) Temperature = 1773K,
proportion of methane =50%

(b) Temperature = 1973K,
proportion of methane =5%

Fig.7 Optical polarizing micrographs of the C/C rods.

Fig.8 Mass gain of carbon (Gas pressure = 4KPa, Proportion of methane = 50%)

(a) Infiltration temperature = 1373K.

(b) Infiltration temperature = 1573K.

(c) Infiltration temperature = 1773K.

(d) Infiltration temperature = 1973K.

Fig.9 Scanning electron micrographs of the fracture surface of the C/C rod after infiltrated 10 hours (4KPa,50%).

(a) 1573K

(b) 1973K

Fig.10 Micrographs of the cross section of C/C rods.

Fig.11 Mass gain of carbon (Temperature = 1573K, proportion of methane =50%)

Fig.12 Mass gain of carbon (Temperature = 1573K, Total gas pressure =4KPa,)